

**RECENT NIGERIAN NOVELS OF GENDER AND THE TRANS-CULTURAL ISSUE:
THE NOVELS OF AKACHI ADIMORA-EZEIGBO, CHIMAMANDA NGOZI ADICHIE
AND GLORIA ERNEST SAMUEL**

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Abstract

A people's culture is a kind of mirror through which their degree of civilization is assessed. However, in a world where the gap in communication that hitherto existed between peoples has almost been literally erased by the internet communication's global village phenomenon, strict cultural distinction and exclusivity can no more be guaranteed. Thus there now exists untrammelled influences across cultures, resulting in the cultures of the stronger and more influential peoples greatly suppressing the cultures of the weaker and, therefore, less influential ones. Through this means, the idea of feminism, which is the idea of women's agitation for equality with men that originated from the West, came to have a very uncomfortable pressure on the African culture. It is the extent of influence that the said Western-originated feminism has had on the quintessential African woman's sense of culture that this work studies in selected novels of the African female writers Akachi Adimora-Ezeigbo, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie and Gloria Ernest-Samuel. Taking a bearing from the backdrop of cultural feminism, the study can find that, at least in principle, while Akachi Adimora-Ezeigbo advocates what she terms the 'snail-sense' feminist approach for the African women to confront their men, so to say, Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie, on her part, wills that all, both men and women, join the feminism train, and Gloria Ernest-Samuel is even more radical in creatively accusing men of exploiting what she perceives as nature's unfairness to the female gender by making them the burden bearers in a childless marriage.

Keywords: Culture, Feminism, Gender, African, Writers
